

FACTORS AFFECTING THE ONLINE PURCHASING BEHAVIOR AMONG UNDERGRADUATES OF UNIVERSITY OF SRI JAYEWARDENEPURA

Hansini Abesinghe¹, Champa Hewagamage², Kaveesha Silva³

*Department of Information Technology, Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce
University of Sri Jayewardenepura*

¹hansiabesinghe1996@gmail.com, ²champah@sjp.ac.lk, ³kaveesha.silva@sjp.ac.lk

Introduction

Nowadays, most people are shifting from traditional to online purchasing patterns because of their busy schedules. Therefore, the Internet has introduced advanced and convenient methods for online purchasing. Online purchasing behavior is a type of behavior that involves consumers' visit websites to search, select and buy products and services.

Even though the Internet has become the most profitable and convenient way to purchase more products and services, most online consumers still prefer to buy offline after using online information as the base (Forsythe and Shi, 2003). In Indonesia and West Sumatra, most people have visited online shopping sites, but only a few are actually purchasing online (Yuannita and Yuannita, 2019; Zuelseptia et al., 2018). The situation in Sri Lanka is also the same. Many consumers prefer to do online purchasing for apparel or less expensive products, but they are reluctant to purchase expensive or hi-tech products due to perceived risk (Withanagamage and Wategama, 2018).

Several factors can influence the consumers' online purchasing behavior. Mostly perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and attitude (Gunawan, et al., 2019; Putra, et al., 2019; Koththagoda and Herath, 2018). Besides those factors, some previous researchers have found that perceived risk plays a major role in consumers' online purchasing behavior (Gershoff and Johar, 2006; Ilmudeen, 2018).

There were some inconveniences among the previous findings in similar research problems. As Syakir and Setiyanto (2019) said, perceived usefulness has a significant positive impact on online purchasing behavior. Ramayah and Ignatius (2005) proved that perceived usefulness has no significant impact on online purchasing behavior. As said by Pena-Garcia, et al., (2020) perceived usefulness has no significant impact on attitude.

Sarkar and Khare (2017) found that perceived ease of use has a negative and insignificant impact on consumer attitudes. Oppositely Gunawan et al., (2019) proved in their research that perceived ease of use has a significant and positive impact on consumer attitudes. Javadi et al., (2012) proved that attitude has a positive significant impact on online purchasing behavior. As said by Jusoh and Ling (2012), attitude has no significant relationship with consumers' online purchasing behavior.

However, In the Sri Lankan context, smaller number of research have been conducted to examine the effect of perceived risk and attitude towards online purchasing behavior with the use of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) model among university undergraduates (Ranasinghe, Kuruppu, Herath, Wijayagrahi, & Mel, 2020). This study aims to examine the relationship between variables, namely, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived risk and attitude and online purchasing behavior, with special reference to management undergraduates of the University of Sri Jayewardenepura.

Methodology

The study will be guided by the researcher's conceptual framework (Figure 1). This model was developed by using the main variables of the TAM model along with the perceived risk and attitude (Gunawan, et al., 2019; Nugroho, 2009; Putra, et al., 2019).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

H1 – Perceived Usefulness has a positive influence on Online Purchasing Behaviour.

H2 – Perceived Usefulness has a positive influence on Attitude.

H3 – Perceived Ease of Use has a positive influence on Attitude.

H4 – Perceived Risk has a negative influence on Online Purchasing Behaviour.

H5 – Attitude has a positive influence on Online Purchasing Behaviour.

This research study used a deductive approach in quantitative research methodology. As a research design, the cross-sectional research design was used. The population of this study was management undergraduates of the University of Sri Jayewardenepura. A sample of undergraduates from the Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce was chosen based on convenience sampling (Galloway 2005). Based on Daniel Sopher's (2021) sample size calculation 2021, the recommended sample size for this study was 177.

In this study, primary data were collected through an online questionnaire. The researcher measured the questions using a Likert scale with five response categories (strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree). Demographic data was analyzed by descriptive data analysis using Microsoft Excel, and for the model testing SmartPLS Professional version was used following the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique.

Results and Discussion

The relationships in the model were tested using partial least squares (PLS). PLS provides an alternative estimation approach to Structural Equation Modeling (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2: SEM Measurements

The measurement model was assessed in terms of the individual factor loading, construct reliability, convergent validity and discriminant validity. Table 1 shows the reliability and validity of the constructs.

Table 1: Construct Reliability and Validity Table

Factor	Factor loading	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
A	0.785 0.728 0.816	0.674	0.820	0.604
OPB	0.719 0.702 0.738 0.720 0.746 0.724	0.821	0.869	0.525
PEU	0.747 0.830	0.850	0.893	0.626

	0.708 0.797 0.863			
PR	0.715 0.759 0.803 0.794	0.771	0.852	0.590
PU	0.731 0.765 0.746 0.796	0.756	0.845	0.577

The factor loading was used to measure the indicator reliability. The standardized indicator loadings ≥ 0.7 is acceptable (Hair, et al., 2017). Internal Consistency Reliability is established in this study because the composite reliability values range and Cronbach's Alpha values range are above the acceptable value of 0.7 or above (Hair, et al., 2017). Convergent validity was also satisfied because all questionnaire items above 0.7 factor loading were selected, and the AVE value of all the variables was greater than 0.5 (Hair, et al., 2017). Since all the diagonal values were higher than other related values, the constructs show acceptable discriminant validity.

Table 2: Path Analysis and Hypotheses Test

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	T Statistics	P Value	Accepted/ Rejected	Confidence Level
H1 – PU has a positive influence on OPB.	0.400	5.139	0.000	Accepted	0.99
H2 – PU has a positive influence on ATU.	0.416	5.741	0.000	Accepted	0.99
H3 – PEU has a positive influence on ATU.	0.213	2.741	0.006	Accepted	0.99
H4 – PR has a negative influence on OPB	-0.251	3.908	0.000	Accepted	0.99
H5 – ATU has a positive influence on OPB	0.292	4.071	0.000	Accepted	0.99

As mentioned above in Table 2, a positive relationship between PU and OPB is confirmed. ($\beta = 0.400$, $t = 5.139$). Therefore, H1 is supported. A positive relationship between PU and ATU is established ($\beta = 0.416$, $t = 5.741$). Therefore, H2 is supported. As predicted, a significantly positive relationship between PEU and ATU is accepted ($\beta = 0.213$, $t = 2.741$). Therefore, H3 is supported. As hypothesized, a negative relationship between PR and OPB is confirmed ($\beta = -0.251$, $t = 3.908$). Therefore, H4 is supported. A positive relationship between ATU and OPB is established ($\beta = 0.292$, $t = 4.071$). Therefore, H5 is supported. PU, ATU and PR have a direct relationship with OPB. PEU has an indirect relationship with the OPB. Even though PU has a direct relationship, it has an indirect relationship as well because of the mediating variable called "Attitude".

Conclusion

The conclusion of this study showed that PU, PEU, PR and ATU have a significant influence on students' online purchasing behavior. Only PU, PR and ATU have a direct impact on the OPB. PEU has an indirect impact on the OPB. Even though PU has a direct impact on the OPB, it also has an indirect impact on the OPB. The findings of this study also recommended significant practical suggestions. In practice, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use must be enhanced. Therefore, the online retailer needs to design their websites user-friendly where the consumer can search, shop and proceed with payments in the easiest possible way. Because then only online vendors can achieve more benefits from their selling. And also, perceived risk must be reduced. Many consumers are concerned about the risk of losing money while receiving no goods or services if they have no prepaid. Therefore, diminishing such risks is important to online vendors. Therefore, an online retailer can apply cash on delivery method of payment or payment via a third party to encourage.

In sum, this study gives a significant contribution to the theory of the TAM model. This study delivers an extra indication of the suitability of using the TAM model to measure the different dimensions of consumers' online purchasing behavior. As examined from the previous TAM model related research in the field of online purchasing, two specific behavioral beliefs (perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use) well explained the

behavior of consumers' online purchasing. In addition, the results of this study have shown that other factors (perceived risk) help us to get a better understanding on the consumers' online purchasing behavior. Therefore, by considering the impact of perceived risk on the consumers' online purchasing behavior power of the TAM model will be greatly enhanced. In sum, this study has important involvement in the theory of the TAM model by providing experimental evidence that PU, PEU, PR, and ATU are important factors that influence the consumers' online purchasing behavior.

Further study should explore other factors that influence online purchasing behavior with a broader range of population and more sample size.

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